

Challenges in creating a biomarker of fetal inflammatory response based on heart rate variability: what are the next steps?

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Abstract

In their recent report (doi:10.1038/s41598-022-05799-3), Magawa et al. validate and extend the initial observations by Durosier et al. (doi: 10.1088/0967-3334/36/10/2089) who had demonstrated that fetal heart rate variability (fHRV) metrics track endotoxin-induced acute fetal inflammatory response in real-time as measured by a composite index of fHRV metrics and IL-6, the key inflammatory cytokine of the fetal inflammatory response. Magawa et al. extend these insights of the fHRV monitoring potential into a preterm gestational age and with a different regime of endotoxin exposure. The authors also recapitulate the negative finding that the chronic phase of the fetal inflammatory response is not readily reflected in the changes of fHRV as analyzed. In this focused mini-review, I discuss the broader implications of the current evidence on fHRV monitoring of inflammation to outline where the full potential of the fHRV monitoring antepartum may lie for early detection and tracking of the inflammatory response. I propose that the key focus for future translational research is to be on establishing the fHRV signature of the memory of fetal inflammation.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of the present focused mini-review is to provide an evidence synthesis on the issue of non-invasive monitoring of the fetal inflammatory response using fetal heart rate variability (fHRV) analysis.

The starting point for the review forms the recent study by Magawa et al. ¹

In this study the authors validated and extended the initial observations by Durosier et al. and Herry et al. ^{2,3} who had demonstrated that fHRV metrics track endotoxin-induced acute fetal inflammatory response in real time as measured by a composite index of fHRV metrics and IL-6, the key inflammatory cytokine of the fetal inflammatory response.

The novel contributions by Magawa et al. are the demonstration of the fHRV monitoring potential at a younger gestational age and with a different regime of endotoxin exposure which seeks to recapitulate the protracted course of fetal inflammation as it may happen in human pregnancy. While any preclinical experimental design remains an approximation of the human physiology, the present independent validation of the ability of fHRV to track the acute phase of fetal inflammatory response is an important result. This is also true for the negative finding that the chronic phase of the fetal inflammatory response does not seem to be reflected in the changes of fHRV as analyzed, similar qualitatively to the three days lasting observations by Durosier et al, but expanded considerably by Magawa et al. to a duration of ten days.

THE EVIDENCE

There are implications of the report by Magawa et al. to consider that will help to develop the full potential of the fHRV monitoring antepartum for early detection and tracking of the inflammatory response.

First, implicit in the animal modeling of fetal inflammatory response is the requirement for fetal electrocardiogram (ECG) signal which can be obtained clinically from transabdominal ECG devices with several now commercially available around the world. This is not trivial to keep in mind, as this technology remains not widely available, albeit the acceptance by the mothers appears to be very broad.⁴

Second, with regard to fHRV analysis, there are distinct differences in the methodological approach of the present work and the prior studies from 2015-2020 that make them complementary in terms of developing future preclinical studies. Magawa et al. chose to focus on the conventional linear HRV metrics in time and frequency domain complemented by the two nonlinear biomarkers of fHRV, sample entropy and asymmetry, which were also computed as they had performed well in clinical studies of early neonatal sepsis detection;⁵ the authors then computed these fHRV metrics in predefined hourly averaged intervals, rather than evaluating sample-by-sample dynamics, and did not demonstrate the concomitant changes in the temporal profile of the pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6. This strategy stands in contrast to the prior studies by Durosier et al. which performed no a

priori selection of particular fHRV metrics, computed them continuously, without hourly averaging, and derived a composite index of fetal inflammatory response, termed the fetal inflammatory index, which comprised a well-defined subset of four HRV metrics deduced via non-supervised machine learning approach from the most complete known set of linear and non-linear HRV metrics currently available.² As reported in this work, the HRV metrics stemmed from the energetic domain: multifractal spectrum cumulant of the first order, time irreversibility asymmetry index (similar to the present study by Magawa et al.); from the informational domain: Allan factor distance from a Poisson distribution and from the invariant domain: the embedding scaling exponent. Notably, the fetal heart rate itself was not part of the fetal inflammatory index. Durosier et al. also clearly demonstrated the concomitant tracking of the IL-6 temporal profile in the acute stage of the inflammatory response.

Overall, it seems clear that fHRV can track fetal inflammatory response in its acute phase. Therein also lies the limitation of the state of the art: in the clinical setting we cannot choose the phase of the inflammatory response.

The existing evidence takes us to the concluding observation that informs future study design: both sets of studies, past and present, agree that the later stage of the inflammatory response (past the first 24h) does not appear to be discernible with the present signal processing techniques based on fHRV metrics. This remains an important field for future research with clear clinical implications: can we identify fetuses who experienced inflammation even after the acute phase, akin to the chronic memory of Zika virus exposure or chronic hypoxia memory demonstrated elsewhere.^{14,15}

EVIDENCE SYNTHESIS

How can we tackle the challenge of discovering the fHRV biomarker of chronic or past inflammation?

To tackle this question, it is beneficial to discuss the underlying motivations in the difference of the approaches between the studies reviewed above from the philosophical epistemological and the applied physiological points of view.

The unsupervised learning approach taken in the former studies makes no attempt at directly tying any given fHRV metric to a physiological behavior. Rather, it assumes the notion of HRV code.⁶ We can understand the fHRV analysis in such experiments to capture the activation of the fetal cholinergic anti-inflammatory pathway⁷ by the endotoxin. It has been reported and discussed that while simple fHRV metrics like RMSSD may reflect the activity of the fetal cholinergic anti-inflammatory pathway somewhat,⁸ the complex network activity of such a pathway cannot be captured by any single fHRV metrics; rather, approaches considering the underlying patterns to be akin to HRV code seem to have a higher chance of succeeding in producing predictive models of physiological behavior.^{6,9} This is broadly in line with the emerging understanding of the network physiology, the modern day reinvention of the systems physiology we have known for well over a century.^{10,11}

The approach taken by Magawa et al. attempts the opposite: select a priori a subset of HRV

metrics believed to be physiologically interpretable or, at least, useful, and evaluate them for the ability to track inflammation.

As I discussed elsewhere, there are fundamental, epistemological limitations to such an approach that limit the generalized inference on the predictive utility of HRV considerably.¹² Physiological assumptions that certain solitary HRV metrics reflect specific contributions from the branches of the autonomic nervous system have been challenged recently, with RMSSD notably not being affected by complete vagal denervation in fetal sheep near term.⁹ Moreover, this strategy has failed us so far in producing any clinically actionable HRV monitoring metrics. Those HRV biomarker discovery strategies that did receive FDA approval for clinical use, e.g., for early sepsis detection, have in fact all been the result of unsupervised machine learning approaches followed by dimensionality reduction.^{5,13}

Taken together, the inability of certain few fHRV metrics to track inflammation singularly, i.e., without any attempt at machine learning on these fHRV metrics as model features or addition of other clinically meaningful multivariate continuous or categorical inputs, cannot, by design, rule out the general ability of the fHRV approach, including over 60 metrics¹⁶ as well as application of machine learning to detect the signature of chronic or past inflammation. This remains an exciting avenue and challenge for future preclinical research and clinical translation.

Additional information

Competing interests

MGF holds patents on fetal monitoring. MGF advises and holds stock in Delfina, an AI-driven mother-child health monitoring company.

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